

EFFECTS OF NEUROPLASTICITY BASED BRAIN-FIT MIND EXERCISES ON NEURO COGNITION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH ATTENTIONAL DEFICITS- A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Brain Gym Exercises significantly improves the neurocognition function of the students. There is a tremendous impact of Brain Gym on the adults, after eight weeks of implementation of brain gym program. There was an increase in memory, cognitive function, concentration, attention and alertness. Effect of Neuroplasticity-based BrainFit® Mind Exercises on Attention Skills of Primary School Students-Ömer Halisdemir University. **Aim of the Study:** The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind Exercises on neuro cognition among college students with attentional deficits.

Objectives of the study

- To assess the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind exercises on attention skills among college students.
- To assess the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind exercises on concentration skills among college students.

Method: 20 Subjects falling in the age of 18-22 yrs, who were noticed as suffering from attention deficit, were separated into two groups. 10 subjects were included in the experimental group and 10 subjects were included under the control group. The experimental group was given neuroplasticity based brain-fit mind exercises. Control group was given the

awareness program of brain gym exercises for a duration of 50 min/day under the supervision of therapist, for 5 days per week for 8 weeks. Outcome measures were applied. **Result:** The data collected were statistically analyzed by paired t-test. From the result of the statistics, it was found out that the neurocognition of the subjects was increased. **Conclusion:** The study concluded that neuroplasticity based brain fit mind exercises was more effective in improving neurocognition among college students with attentional deficits.

KEYWORDS: Brain fit mind exercise, cognition, attention, attention deficit, attention and concentration scale.

INTRODUCTION

Neuroplasticity is the brain's ability to change and adapt due to experience. It is an umbrella term referring to the brain's ability to change, reorganize or grow neural networks. This can involve functional changes due to brain damage or structural changes due to learning.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind Exercises on neurocognition among college students with attentional deficits.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind exercises on attention skills among college students.
- To assess the effect of neuroplasticity based brain fit mind exercises on concentration skills among college students.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A pilot study was conducted for a period of 8 weeks during FEB-APR 2024, where the 20 samples were recruited based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria

- Age ranging between 18-22yrs
- Both the genders can participate
- Under and Post graduate college students are included
- Those who are having MMSE score above 24
- Right dominant subjects
- Willing to participate

Exclusion criteria

- Those who are having difficulty to comprehend language
- Those who are having auditory or visual disorder
- Previous history of depression or psychosis
- Those who have undergone eye surgeries
- Smart phone addicts
- Those who are having dyspnoea
- Those who skip breakfast regularly, poor nutrition and less physical activities.

OUTCOME MEASURES

Attention

Concentration

MATERIAL USED

- **Mindful Attention Awareness scale (MAAS)**
- **Concentration Questionnaire**

PROCEDURE

A pilot study was conducted for a period of 8 weeks, where the samples were recruited based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Written informed consent was obtained from the samples. The total number of samples was 20 which was divided into two groups, namely Group A -10 samples (experimental) and Group B-10 samples (control) group. The experimental group was given neuroplasticity based brain-fit mind exercises. Control group was given the awareness program of brain gym exercises. Outcome measures were applied. Pre and post test scores was analysed based on the statistical analysis. Also the reliability and validity of the outcome measures were verified. Totally Neuroplasticity based brain-fit mind exercises was given to the samples for a duration of 50 min/day under the supervision of therapist, for 5 days per week for 8 weeks.

PROTOCOL

Group A-Experimental Group

Neuroplasticity based Brain-fit mind exercises was given to the Group A (Experimental group) samples which included the following:

1. Training a new language

Duolingo App

Preferably French or

Any language as per their convenience

Alphabets -5 min

Words -5min

Duration:10min

2. Preferring activities in non-dominant hand

Writing and Drawing patterns - 5min

Holding coffee mug with coffee in non-dominant hand- 5min

Duration-10min

3. Aerobic exercises includes

⊙ Speed walking

⊙ Skipping

⊙ 2 min of warm up session and

⊙ 8 min of exercises making a total duration of 10min

4. Brain gym exercises includes:

⊙ Cross crawl

⊙ Think of X

⊙ Lazy Eight

⊙ Neck rolls

⊙ Brain button

⊙ All the exercises are performed one session/ day , each for 2 min making a total of 10min

⊙ All the exercises are performed one session/ day , each for 6 min making a total of 30min

Higher Level Reasoning (Critical Thinking, Problem - Solving, Auditory and more)

CROSS CRAWL

It can help release the stress and concentrate better on studies.

The Lazy-8

Start here

Neck Roll

- Sit upright or stand
- Roll neck slowly all the way around
- Do it with your eyes closed or open
- Do it in both directions

Sending messages from the right brain hemisphere to the left side of the body, and vice versa.

BRAIN BUTTON

Increase the flow of electromagnetic energy

Think of an X to Improve Learning and Confidence

- Thinking of an "X" can:
- ~ reinforce whole-brain and whole-body co-ordination for ease of thought, communication and performance.
 - ~ helps with speed-reading
 - ~ assists with sports co ordination and play activities

5. Meditation

- ☉ **Make the sample sit in a comfortable posture in a calm environment**
- ☉ **Ask them to notice and feel their breath**
- ☉ **Slowly meditate**

Duration 10min

Totally Neuroplasticity based brain-fit mind exercises was given to the samples for a duration of 50 min/day under the supervision of therapist, for 5 days per week for 8 weeks.

Group B-Control Group

Control group(Group B) was given the awareness program of brain gym exercises. Outcome measures were applied. Pre and post test scores was analyzed.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was done. Pre test and post test values of the control group and experimental group were statistically analyzed by means of t-test. The posttest values of experimental and control group were analysed by chi square test .The significance levels used for this study was $P < 0.05$.

Table: 1-Experimental Group.

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	ATTENTION	3.68	10	.649	.205
	V4	4.21	10	.626	.198
Pair 2	CONCENTRATION	10.80	10	3.795	1.200
	V6	5.70	10	3.683	1.165

Paired Samples Test				
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	ATTENTION - V4	-5.771	9	.000
Pair 2	CONCENTRATION - V6	4.967	9	.001

Table 2: Control Group.

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	ATTENTION	3.55	10	.506	.160
	V4	3.93	10	.712	.225
Pair 2	CONCENTRATION	9.40	10	4.222	1.335
	V6	6.50	10	3.749	1.186

Paired Samples Statistics					
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ATTENTION SCORES-EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

ATTENTION SCORES-CONTROLGROUP

CONCENTRATION SCORES-EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

CONCENTRATION SCORES-CONTROL GROUP

RESULT

From the pre and post test scores, it was evident that Neuroplasticity based brain fit mind was more effective on neurocognition among college students with attentional deficits.

DISCUSSION

The statistical analysis was done which revealed that the mean post test score of attention was 4.211 which was higher than the mean pre-test score 3.684 and it gave an inference that the

attention of the group A (experimental group) has increased. In case of control group, the mean post test score of attention was 3.937 which was higher than the mean pre-test score 3.556 and it gave an inference that the attention of the group B (control group) has also increased. However, when comparing both the experimental and control group, the post test scores of attention of the experimental group has been found to be much more significant than the control group at $P > 0.001$. Dr. chaitanya kulkarni, 2019 has stated that the effect of brain gym exercises shows significant improvement in attention skill among young adults. With relevance to concentration, the mean pre-test score of the concentration in the experimental group was 10.8, which has been reduced to 5.7 in the mean post-test score. Higher the scores, lower will be the concentration and vice versa. On comparison of both the experimental and control group, the post test score of concentration of the experimental group has been found to be much more significant at $P > 0.001$ than the control group.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that Neuroplasticity based brain fit mind was more effective on neurocognition among college students with attentional deficits.

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